

Detection and Localization of Water Leakage in Water Supply System using Machine Learning Techniques: Application to the BattLeDIM Benchmark

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ABSTRACT

Water leakage issue is a global preoccupation in the field of Water Supply System (WSS) field, particularly given the present-day scarcity of water resources. The detection and localization of water leaks is a complex challenge, predominantly due to their potential to remain undetected for long periods of time. The occurrence of this phenomenon depends on the level of system maintenance, as it manifests in junction and/or pipes due to uncontrolled actions and it can range from 3% to over 50% [1]. Furthermore, the Portuguese regulator ERSAR [2] reported in 2023 that the actual water leakage in Portugal's supply system was 5.5 m³/(km day) for the bulk side and 2.4 m³/(km day) for the distribution side. Several leakage management measures can be implemented to minimize the water leakage, including preventive measures, assessment protocols, regulatory and control measures, detection and localization techniques, and repair initiatives [3]. The detection and localization techniques comprise hardware- and software-based methods which, integrating Machine Learning (ML) models, can represent a powerful automated data analysis and hydraulic simulation tool. These developments can also lead to substantial advancements for a faster leakage detection and localization.

This work aims to provide a scientific overview of the detection and localization methodologies in WSS. A sub-framework based on ML techniques has been proposed for the detection of anomalies in pressure data time series. This is implemented in a benchmark case study presented by Vrachimis *et al.* [4] called BattLeDIM network, where various ML models were tested and compared with previous baseline results.

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